

Ideal Gas Law, Quantum Thermodynamics and Pure Bound States

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In (1) the ideal gas result $P V^\gamma = \text{constant}$ ((1)) where $\gamma = c_p/c_v = 5/3$ is applied to a pure quantum bound state for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls and it is seen that ((1)) is a constant just as in the case of an ideal gas. This, however, depends on the result $PV = nRT$. {An ideal gas, however, follows from a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution which is linked to the equipartition theorem. The value $c_p/c_v = 5/3$ reflects this. } Furthermore, T and V are distinct physical variables for an ideal gas. For a particle in a well with infinite potential walls, $E = \text{constant}/L^2$. The energy depends only on L whereas in an ideal gas it only depends on T i.e. $E = 3/2 T$.

In this note we try to analyze why the ideal gas relationship ((1)) holds for a particle in a box with infinite walls. We also try to link the relationship E proportional to $1/L^2$ to scaling features which ensure that $S = S_p(n) + S_x$ does not depend on L allowing for an adiabatic transformation to keep entropy constant. (This holds for both a particle in a box and a harmonic oscillator.) We use the thermodynamical law $dE = TdS - PdV$ and find that $PV = nRT$ only holds in the one dimensional gas i.e. $PL = \text{constant}$ T . In such a case we are able to justify ((1)), but not in the 3-D situation.

Ideal Gas Law

The ideal gas law is associated with a number of relationships:

$PV = nRT$ ((1a)) P =pressure, V =volume T =temperature n =number of moles and R =constant

$E = 3/2 nRT$ ((1b)) E =energy $P V^\gamma = \text{constant}$ where $\gamma = c_p/c_v = 5/3$ ((2))

((1b)) shows that energy depends on a variable T (temperature). Physically this is completely different from volume. In fact, one may hold the volume fixed and increase or decrease temperature. The factor $3/2$ in ((1b)) shows the idea of the equipartition theorem i.e. 3 represents the x-y-z directions and $1/2 R T$ is the energy in each direction. The above results are consistent with the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, but one does not really need this specific distribution to find situations which may be written in terms similar to ((1a)) and ((1b)). The question in such cases, however, is what is T ? It is a parameter which may be chosen to incorporate various constants so that only the geometrical $3/2$ or $5/3$ factor remains.

We use (2) to show how ((2)) arises. For an adiabatic process:

$C_v dT = -pdV$ as $TdS=0$. Here $c_v = 3/2 nR$ i.e. $E = 3/2 nRT$.

Furthermore $PV = nRT$ so $(dP)V + P dV = nR dT$. Combining these two and eliminating dT leads to ((2)).

A main point we wish to make is that one may consider ((1a)) and ((1b)) together with the thermodynamic relationship for an isentropic process i.e. $dE=TdS-PdV \rightarrow dE=-PdV$. In one dimension $dE=-PdL$. In such a case, if E is a function solely of L , then $-P=dE/dL$. If further E is proportional to L to a power, then $PL = \text{constant}$. As a result one may create a parameter based on L to a certain power multiplied by various constants and call this T . In such a case one may "create" the forms $E=3/2 T$ parameter. We try to show in further sections that this approach may be applied to a bound state for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls. In such a case $E_n = n^2 \pi^2 \hbar^2 / 2mL^2$. One may use dE_n/dL to find $-P$, but then combine $1/L^2$ with constants to create $E_n = 3/2 T(n)$ where $T(n)$ is a kind of temperature which applies for a fixed n . It is a function of L , however, which is physically completely different from the ideal gas case. In the next section we consider the definition of entropy and show how it behaves if one changes L such that the energy state n stays the same i.e. a quantum adiabatic transformation.

Entropy for a Particle in a Box with Infinite Potential Walls

The time-dependent Schrodinger equation may be written as:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} W + V(x) W = E W(x) \quad ((3))$$

Let us set $m=1$ because there is a fixed particle rest mass - it is not a parameter. It is possible, however, to have other parameters in the system. For example, for a particle in a box with infinite potential, the box exists from $[0,L]$ and there exists the parameter L which is found in boundary conditions. For an oscillator there is k the spring constant.

We consider trying to make the "parameter" disappear so that one has:

$$H(y) W(y) = E_{\text{mod}} W(y) \text{ which is parameterless } ((4))$$

To do so, one may multiply ((3)) by $1/b$ $1/b$ so that $y=bx$. In such a case $V(x)/bb$ must be parameterless and E/bb as well.

For a spring $V(x)=.5kx^2$ so $k/(bb^2)$ should be parameterless as should E/bb . This suggests $b=k^{1/4}$. For a particle in a box with infinite walls, $V(x)=0$ within $[0,L]$, but E goes as $1/L^2$ so $b=1/L$. With this general prescription, one may write density as:

$$P(x) = b W(y)W(y) \text{ such that } \int dx W(x) = \int dx b W(y)W(y) = 1 \quad ((5))$$

$W(x)=\sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ where $a(p)$ is the Fourier transform. If one uses $y=bx$, then p changes to $p/b = z$. Thus:

$$P(p) = 1/b \ a(z)a(z) \text{ such that } \int P(p)dp = \int dp/b \ a(z)a(z) = 1 \quad ((6))$$

As a result $P(x)$ contains a b factor and $P(p)$ a $1/b$ factor. Using Shannon's formula one may find entropy using $P(x)P(p)$ i.e.

$$S/(-k) = \int dpdx P(x)P(p) \ln[P(p)P(x)] = \int dx P(x) \ln(P(x)) + \int dp P(p) \ln(P(p))$$

$$= \int dy W(y) \ln(W(y)) + \ln(b) + \ln(1/b) \int dz P(z) \ln(P(z)) \quad ((7))$$

$\ln(b) + \ln(1/b) = 0$ for both the oscillator and particle in a box with infinite walls. Thus, if one changes k or L , but the energy level remains constant i.e. a quantum adiabatic transformation $S=S_x+S_p$ stays constant. In other words the quantum adiabatic transformation for a pure bound state is also isentropic. Furthermore, the energy of the state is linked to the parameter as shown above i.e.

$$E_n/bb \text{ is parameter free } ((8))$$

For the oscillator with $m=1$, E_n must contain the factor \sqrt{k} and for the particle in a box with infinite potential E_n must contain the factor $1/(LL)$ as they both do.

Thermodynamics for a Quantum Particle in a Box with Infinite Potential Walls

In the above section it was found that E is proportional to $1/(bb)$ or $1/(LL)$. This holds in both 1 and 3 dimensions.

For a quantum adiabatic transformation one may use the thermodynamic relationship:

$$dE = TdS - PdV \quad ((10)) \text{ with } dS=0$$

It was shown in the above section that $dS=0$ if L changes and n , the energy level, remains constant. Thus:

$$dE = -PdL \quad ((11)) \text{ for one dimension or three dimensions. It is seen that } E=b/(LL) \text{ so:}$$

$$PL = b_1 E \text{ where } b_1 = \text{constant for } n \text{ fixed for both 1 and 3D } \quad ((12))$$

This is almost of the form of the ideal gas law where $PV=2/3E$ with $E=3/2 T$. The number 3 represents the 3 spatial dimensions and implies an isotropic system. $T/2$ is the energy in one dimension. It should be noted again that for the ideal gas T and V are physically different. For the quantum particle in the box one may create a parameter which has the appearance of T . It turns out to be proportional to $1/LL$ which is peculiar because this means that L and T are directly linked unlike the ideal gas case. Furthermore, one must be careful to choose the parameter T such that energy is $T/2$ and there is an equipartition of energy i.e. $E=3/2 T$. This suggests a particle in a box with $L_x=L_y=L_z=L$. For this problem in 3D with $n_x=n_y=n_z=1$

$$E = (1/2m) 3 \cdot 2 \cdot 3.14 / (LL) \text{ so } T = 1/LL (1/2m) 2 \cdot 2 \cdot 3.14 \quad ((13)) \text{ so } E = 3/2 T.$$

$$\text{Next one uses } dE/dL = -P \text{ or } PL = 2E = 3T \quad ((14))$$

This differs from the ideal gas case where one has: $PV = T = 2/3 E$.

Using ((13)) and ((14)) to eliminate dT yields:

$$dP/P + dV \{ V^{-2/3}/3 + 2V^{-1/3} \} = 0 \quad ((15)) \text{ which is not the ideal gas result of ((2))}$$

Nevertheless, it is shown in (1) the ideal gas law result holds for a pure quantum bound state i.e. for $PV = b E$ (which violates $-P = dE/dL$ for both 1 and 3D) while thermodynamics yields $PL = b_1 E$.

$$P V^{5/3} = E/V V^{5/3} = 1(\text{LLLLL}) \quad \text{LLLLL constant} = \text{constant} \quad ((15))$$

It seems, however, that the ideal gas result holds in the quantum case with thermodynamics if one uses only one dimension. In such a case $E = \frac{1}{2} T$ and $PL = T$. Then one has:

$$P(L)^3 = E/L \quad \text{LLL} = \text{constant} \quad ((16))$$

Thus a one dimensional pure state of a particle in a box with infinite potential walls together with the thermodynamic relation $dE = TdS - PdL$ does seem to follow the adiabatic form from the ideal gas law. P here is the pressure in the direction of L .

For 3 dimensions with different n_x , n_y and n_z values, one may have P_x , P_y and P_z .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider that for both the quantum oscillator and a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, if one tries to eliminate a parameter i.e. k for the oscillator or L for the box by creating a new variable $y = bx$ then energy E becomes E/bb and should also be parameterless. This suggests that E goes as \sqrt{k} or $1/LL$ for the two cases. In addition, $P(x) = b W(y)W(y)$ and $P(p) = 1/b a(z)a(z)$ where $y = bx$ and $z = p/b$ so entropy $S = S_x + S_p$ does not contain the parameter. Thus for a particle in a box S does not depend on L and if one has a quantum adiabatic transformation i.e. n stays constant then so does S . As a result one may think of E as a function of bb e.g. $1/(LL)$ i.e. $E = b_1/LL$. Using the thermodynamic relation with $dS = 0$ yields $dE = -PdV$. In one dimension, one may define a parameter T such that $E = \frac{1}{2} T$. This means T is proportional to $1/LL$ which is different from the ideal gas case where T and V are physically distinct. Nevertheless with this transformation one may show that the ideal case isentropic relationship follows for one dimension i.e. $PLLL = \text{constant}$. Interestingly $PV^{5/3} = \text{constant}$ as well, but this requires the relationships $PV = T$ and $E = 3/2T$. $PV = T$ violates the thermodynamic result $dE = -PdL$ i.e. from thermodynamics $-P$ is proportional to $1/(LLL)$ while $PV = T$ suggests that P is proportional to $1/(LLLLL)$.

References

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